

Connecting Sabang to Merauke: Indonesia's Efforts on Realizing Broadband Connectivity in 2030¹

Iwan Setiawan <stwn at unsoed.ac.id>

Introduction

Indonesia is one of South East Asian countries considered to be growing and is expected to be the world's seventh-largest economy in 2030 [1]. As the largest island country in the world that consists of more than 17,000 islands scattered across the archipelago, with a projected population of 299 million inhabitants in 2030 [2] and 64.8% Internet penetration in 2018 with 10.12% user growth from the previous year [3], Indonesia needs to “unite” the isles and the people digitally. The situation demands its development and economic acceleration in this information era towards the coming year.

One needed effort to realize these is by laying a foundation for broadband connectivity. This so-called national backbone network reaches all cities and regencies, including rural and remote areas. If the backbone has been provisioned, the second goal is how to use this “digital superhighway” to support its missions of bringing national welfare to Indonesian people from Sabang to Merauke, west to the east, by giving them opportunities to access services through the network and to be involved in regional and global digital economy.

National Backbone for Indonesians

Consortiums of public and private network/telecommunication operators have been formed to build the Palapa Ring, a nationwide backbone network with fiber-optic land and submarine cables connecting cities and regencies across the country. This project is not a “one-night project” since there were former efforts initiated in 1998 with the Nusantara 21 but hampered by the economic crisis, unrealized projects of the National Optical Fibre Ring and Palapa O2 Ring in 2005, and the Palapa Ring plan in 2007. Finally, it became fruitful in 2016 when the Palapa Ring “second edition” started to be reinitiated and completed 100% in 2018 and 2019 [4]. Figure 1 shows the map of the Palapa Ring project with three packages: West, Central, and East rings, connected to the national backhaul.

Figure 1. Palapa Ring map (baktikominfo.id)

The original target plan for the Palapa Ring project is to provision 35,280 km of submarine cables and 21,807 km of land cables connecting cities/regencies in Indonesia [5]. With the existing networks already built by public

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and private network operators covering several parts of the country, especially by a state-owned company, PT Telkom Indonesia, constructing the optical fiber networks in 457 regencies, the remaining goal for the project is 57 that are commercially inviable [6]. It has more than 12,000 km of land and submarine cables, plus 66 microwave hops. The costs are shared among consortium members without the state budget (APBN).

As part of Indonesia's Universal Service Obligation (USO), this project aims to build high-speed nationwide backbone network infrastructure, particularly for underdeveloped, frontier, and outermost areas (3T), so that broadband connectivity can be accessed from all regions in Indonesia. By bringing broadband networks to all parts of the country, Indonesians, especially from the 3T areas, could access many digital services and join the national/regional/global economy. Because the backbone reaches all regions via their capitals, long-distance network or Internet access costs will be lower. It also promises to narrow the digital divide and literacy gaps.

Towards Digital Connectivity and Services in 2030

All capitals of cities and regencies in Indonesia are connected to the national backbone network through the Palapa Ring project, which provides broadband access to the country. This development is also followed by broader coverage of mobile cellular networks. Based on administration area/division with coverage of 100% signal or residential areas with more than 50%, it is stated that 423 cities/regencies (82.3%) are covered by 4G [7]. However, the author assumes these percentages only include the capitals and their near surroundings since there are still 7,971 "blank spot" villages [7].

According to the national medium-term development plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024, Indonesia's target for building base transceiver stations (BTS) or last-mile is 5,052 non-commercial villages until 2024. In three years, starting 2020 to 2022, the Satria satellite will be constructed, and it is planned to serve the country in 2023 at 150 Gbps rate. Regarding the fixed broadband with fiber-optic networks, the projected percentages of the coverage are 36.42%, 37.15%, 42.85%, 50%, and 60.60% districts for 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024, respectively. Regional data centers hosting computing and storage, possibly serving with cloud technologies, will gradually be built for provincial/cities/regencies from 30% in 2020 to 100% in 2024. Digital broadcasting infrastructure is also set up with 283 transmission unit locations. All these indicators are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Digital transformation target indicators for RPJMN 2020-2024 [7]

Target	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
BTS/Last-mile	5,052	5,052	5,052	5,052	5,052
Satria satellite	Construction	Construction	Construction	150 Gbps	150 Gbps
Districts covered by fiber-optic netw.	36,42%	37,15%	42,85%	50,00%	60,60%
Data centers in prov./cities/regencies	30%	50%	80%	100%	100%
Digital broadcasting	44 locations	50 locations	60 locations	74 locations	55 locations

The digital infrastructure can be used for many applications or services. Smart City is one of these that will support the effort by piloting 25 cities and regencies starting from 2017 with the "1000 Smart Cities" program, including Jambi City in Sumatra, West Indonesia, to Mimika Regency in Papua, East Indonesia [8]. Another potential digital service in Indonesia is e-business, such as e-commerce, currently popular in the form of online marketplaces. These means give small and medium enterprises, even the micro ones, opportunities to reach markets easily through the network or Internet access provided by fixed or mobile broadband connected to the Palapa Ring national backbone network. Indonesians also need online or distance learning since schools and universities are generally far from 3T areas. Additionally, digital broadcasting can be used to stream educational content.

The three cases are only examples that the author has seen multiple times. With the data centers distributed in provinces, cities, and regencies, people could access services faster and more efficiently. These services are not only important in normal situations but also urgent in the pandemic that people need to work and study at home.

In the end, most people will finally get used to accessing online services during or after this pandemic. With the “new normal,” broadband connectivity will be required, and it is not just a nice-to-have.

Conclusions

The role of Palapa Ring as a nationwide backbone network that will span across the country will not only give broadband connectivity to many Indonesians, especially in 3T areas, but also opportunities for them to connect to their fellow citizens and be involved in the digital economy regionally and globally. This situation would digitally make the “unity in diversity,” the national motto, more real. The future challenge for 5-10 years for Indonesia's broadband connectivity development is to build network extensions that branch out from the backbone and finally reach villages with reliable access networks/last-mile, fixed (fiber-optic), or wireless (4G). Satria satellite could help tackle the challenge, but currently, no mechanism has been devised to access it, either via ground stations as nodes in districts connecting to local networks or other means.

The indicators of RJPMN are the signs of the nation's desire to realize them. However, the author thinks that 4G needs to reach most of the 3T areas in 2030, but this situation might be changed if all national stakeholders work hand-in-hand to accelerate the realization. The other option for the communities in those areas is to start to learn and build their networks themselves, for example, by constructing local fixed wireless networks based on 802.11ac (Gigabit Wireless), even 3G/4G mobile cellular with OpenBTS or other similar open platforms. If this is the case, the government needs to facilitate the provisioning of the networks that will interconnect with the national backbone, including “permissive” policies such as licensing. This way, the bottom-up will meet the top-down approach, and hopefully, everyone will be happy.

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